

THE EFFECT OF RECEIPT OF ZISWAF FUNDS, WADIAH GIRO SAVINGS, AND MURABAHAH INCOME ON OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY RATIO (OER/BOPO) WITH FIRM SIZE AS MODERATING VARIABLE IN ISLAMIC BANKING IN INDONESIA PERIOD 2018.Q1 – 2023.Q3

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to test and analyze the effect of receiving funds ZISWAF, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income against BOPO moderated by firm size. The sample used is banking financial reports sharia from Q1 2018 until Q3 2023, with technique taking sample use purposive sampling which produced 115 financial reports during the six periods year. The data analysis methods used include Panel Data Regression Analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis using the Eviews 12 application. Results of this study indicated that reception funds ZISWAF, savings giro wadiah And Murabaha income does not have a significant influence on BOPO in the sector sharia banking during the 2018-2023 period. Firm Size is incapable of moderating influence reception funds ZISWAF, savings giro wadiah, nor income murabahah to BOPO in sector banking sharia during period the. It is recommended for future research to consider the use of variables additional moderation and involving samples from various industry sectors, so that the results research can provide broader and more representative insights from a variety of sector economy.

Keywords: *Reception Funds ZISWAF, Wadiah Giro Savings, Murabahah Income, Operational Efficiency Ratio (OER/BOPO), Firm Size, Islamic Banking*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Islamic banking industry in Indonesia has recorded rapid growth. This growth is driven by increasing public awareness of the principles sharia principles in finance, which results in high demand for product And service banking sharia (Wasiaturrahma, 2022). Industry banking sharia Indonesia develop Good in amount nor performance institution his finances. The main Islamic banking products are based on profit sharing patterns, apart from it also covers non-profit sharing and

various funding and financing products service finance and non-financial (Coal et al., 2023).

Besides works as intermediary finance, banking sharia Also own not quite enough answer social, like reception funds ZISWAF And distribution to institution manager zakat. Product banking sharia Also covers giro wadiah And murabahah. Giro wadiah is type savings Which possible customers interesting funds When just, with bank sharia responsible answer on risk loss (Munawaroh et al., 2022). Murabaha is transaction in where bank sell goods with profit Which has agreed previously with customers. Wrong One superiority product murabahah is customers can obtain goods in accordance with condition finance they through instalment Which has agreed (Prabowo, 2009).

Receipt of ZISWAF funds, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income can influence the BOPO ratio which is moderated by firm size. Large firm size demonstrate stronger abilities in reducing deficits and coping economic problems because they have more financial resources and capabilities. Study This aims to analyze the effect of receiving ZISWAF funds, current account savings wadiah, and murabahah income against BOPO with firm size as a variable moderation from year 2018 Q1 to 2023 Q3.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

ZISWAF

Zakat, infaq, sadaqah, And waqf (ZISWAF) is form worship Which aims to carry out obedience to Allah and social responsibility among fellow man. Funds ZISWAF used for reduce gap social between person rich And poor, so that push creation balance economy (Septianah & Vahlevi, 2021). Sharia banking in Indonesia has an important role in distributing ZISWAF funds. Apart from being a financial institution that collects funds from customer, banking sharia Also role as agent social Which ensure distribution riches Which more evenly (Aristoni, 2018).

Wadiah Current Account

Wadiah is a term that refers to the process of depositing goods or funds to a party Which responsible answer For look after it And return it When even requested by the owner (Indria, 2014). Fatwa Board Sharia National stipulates that wadiah giro must have the nature of a deposit, which means the funds are must always be available to be withdrawn by the owner whenever needed. Besides that, in giro wadiah No yes requires rewards whatever Which nature must to customers (Ali, 2021)

Income Murabaha

Murabahah is a sale and purchase agreement where the initial price of goods is mutually determined with additional profits agreed upon by the seller and buyer. In In this contract, the seller conveys the initial price of the goods transparently to the buyer and adding a profit margin as part of the overall price must be paid. Murabaha income is obtained from the difference between the purchase prices goods by seller And price sell Which paid by buyer (Nuzuri & Adriani, 2018).

Cost Operational Income Operational (BOPO)

BOPO is indicator Which measure efficiency performance bank in produce profit. A lower BOPO value indicates higher bank efficiency. Ratio This compare cost operational with income operational bank, Which indicates the bank's ability to optimize income with costs minimal (Khatimah et al., 2020). Operating costs include all expenses related to bank operations, such as employee salaries, administrative costs, and asset maintenance costs. Meanwhile, operating income covers everything receipts originating from the bank's main activities, such as profit sharing and income from other banking services.

Firm Size

Firm size is a descriptive indicator financial strength and capacity operational A company. *Firm Size* No only reflect big capital Which invested in company, but Also show the company's ability to manage risk, expand and survive in condition market that fluctuates (Krishnando & Novitasari, 2021).

Influence Reception Funds ZISWAF against BOPO

Funds ZISWAF obtained through zakat, infaq, sadaqah, And waqf in economy Islam. Zakat is obligation for every Muslim, temporary infaq, sadaqah, And waqf is method give to fellow Muslim. ZISWAF is practice distribute riches in economy Islam For carry out order Allah And fulfill responsibilities social (Sugita & Wulandari, 2020). Study previous stated that receiving ZISWAF funds could improve financial performance sharia banking. However, the effect on BOPO is not significant due to funds zakat is source funds limited Which No influential big to performance finance banking sharia (Faith et al., 2022).

H1: Reception funds ZISWAF No influential to BOPO.

Influence Savings Giro Wow against BOPO

Improvement amount savings giro wadiah can impact positive on ratio BOPO. Study previous state that with reduce expenditure operational And increase efficiency, giro wadiah can help increase profit operational as well as reduce cost marketing, Which in a way overall can supports improving the financial performance of Islamic banks (Renjani & Hendrawati, 2020). H2: Current account savings wadiah influence on BOPO.

Influence Income Murabaha to BOPO

Income Murabaha is profit Which obtained by bank sharia through murabahah transactions (Setyaji & Musaroh, 2018). Income from transactions Murabaha can affect the BOPO ratio. Previous research states that BOPO own connection positive to income margins murabaha, signifies that improving operational efficiency and cost management can contribute on improvement income from transaction murabahah (Lubis et al., 2023).

H3: Income murabahah influential to BOPO.

Influence Reception Funds ZISWAF against BOPO Moderated Firm Size

Reception funds ZISWAF can be used as source funds for carry out bank operations, such as business financing, capital loans, and scholarships. Previous research states that ZISWAF fund receipts can be used as source funds for do operation bank, like financing business, capital loans, and scholarships. In banks with a large firm size, acceptance ZISWAF funds can have a greater influence on BOPO because the funds are more can be used to perform more banking operations. At the bank with a small firm size, receipt of ZISWAF funds can have more influence small to BOPO Because funds Which more limited (Sunarsih & Dahlifah, 2023).

H4: Firm size capable moderate reception funds ZISWAF to BOPO.

Influence Savings Giro Wow to BOPO Moderated Firm Size

Influence savings giro wadiah to BOPO banking sharia can varies depends on size company (firm size). Study previous stated that in banks with a large firm size, wadiah demand deposits tends to have a positive impact on BOPO due to the availability of funds big possible bank For do operation like financing business, capital loans, and scholarships. Apart from that, wadiah giro savings can help reduce need liquidity bank in term short. In side other, in bank with With a small firm size, the influence of Wadiah demand deposits on BOPO tends to be greater limited due to limited funds available for bank operations (Hasibuan et al., 2023).

H5: Firm size capable moderate savings giro wadiah to BOPO .

Influence Income Murabaha to Bopo Moderated Firm Size

The influence of murabahah income on BOPO in the banking industry Sharia can be influenced by company size (*firm size*). Previous research state that income murabahah in bank with *firm size* Which big tends to have a positive influence on BOPO due to the availability of funds big possible bank For do operation like financing business, loan capital, And scholarship. Besides That, income murabahah Also can help reduce bank operational costs in the short term. While at the bank with Small firm size, the influence of murabahah income on BOPO is more limited Because limitations funds Which available For operational bank. (Masyithah, 2022).

H6: Firm size capable moderate income murabahah to BOPO .

Influence Reception Funds Ziswaf, Savings Giro Wow, And Income Murabaha to Bopo

Influence reception funds Ziswaf, savings giro wadiah, And income Murabahah towards BOPO in the Islamic banking industry can vary. Study previously stated that the receipt of Ziswaf funds, wadiah giro savings, and Murabaha income has the potential to provide a positive influence on BOPO Because funds Which obtained from sources the can used For supports bank operations and reduces operational costs in the short term (Khatimah et al., 2020).

H7: ZISWAF fund receipts, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income in a way simultaneously affect BOPO.

Picture 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Processed by writer (2024)

III. METHODOLOGY

This research uses quantitative methods with secondary data consisting of from banking financial reports from the first quarter of 2018 to the third quarter year 2023. Technique taking sample use purposive sampling. Sample study covers 115 report finance from 5 company banking during that period. Data analysis methods include Panel Data Regression Models and Analysis Regression Moderation. Here's the equation model in analysis regression data panel:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + e_i \text{ Where:}$$

Y = BOPO

α = Constant

β = Coefficient Regression

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF Funds X2 = savings giro wadiah

X3 = murabahah income e_i = Error

Test hypothesis use Analysis Regression Moderation with form equality analysis as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3Z + \beta_4X_1*Z + \beta_5X_2*Z + e$$

Where:

Y = BOPO

α = Constant

β = Coefficient Regression

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF Funds X2 = savings giro wadiah

X3 = murabahah income Z = Firm Size

X1*Z = Interaction of the influence of receiving ZISWAF funds with moderation of

firm size X2*Z = Interaction of the influence of wadiah demand deposits with

moderation of firm size X3*Z = Interaction influence income murabahah with

moderation firm size

ei = Error

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

DISCUSSION Results Study

Analysis Descriptive

Table 1. Statistics Descriptive

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	25082.01	3397786.	893883.6	90.86165	16.65089
Maximum	669879.0	27797852	11354171	202.7400	19.58335
Minimum	0.000000	12930.00	1682,000	64.64000	14.11809
Std. Dev.	87500.44	6651346.	2098803.	14.72556	1.474195
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

Based on Table 1, study use 115 sample from report finance banking covering the period from 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3. On variables receipt of ZISWAF funds (X1), the results of descriptive statistics in table 1 show that mark average is 25082.01, mark maximum 669879.0, mark minimum 0.000000, And standard deviation 87500.44.

For the wadiah current account savings variable (X2), the results of descriptive statistics are in table 1 shows that the average value is 3397786, the maximum value is 27797852, the minimum 12930.00, and standard deviation 6651346.

For the murabahah income variable (X3), the results of descriptive statistics are in table 1 shows that the average value is 893883.6, the maximum value is 11354171, the minimum 1682,000, and standard deviation 2098803.

For the BOPO variable (Y), the results of descriptive statistics in table 1 show that mark average is 90.86165, median 94.91000, mark maximum 202.7400, mark minimum 64.64000, and standard deviation 14.72556.

Final, on variable firm size (Z), results statistics descriptive in table 1 shows that the average value is 16.65089, the maximum value is 19.58335, the minimum 14.11809, and standard deviation 1.474195.

Election Model Regression Data Panel

Stages This aim For choose method Which most appropriate in between *Common Effects, Fixed Effect, or Random Effect.*

Test Chow

Table 2. Results Test Chow

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	4.827259	(4,107)	0.0013
Cross-section Chi-square	19.078813	4	0.0008

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

The results of the Chow test show that the cross-section chi-square probability value is 0.0008, which is lower than 0.05. So it can be concluded that *the Fixed Effect Model (FEM)* is model that most appropriate For used in analysis This.

Test Hausman

Table 3. Results Test Hausman

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Cross-section random	19.296402	3	0.0002

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

The Hausman test results show a probability of 0.0002, which is lower from 0.05. So it can be concluded that *the Fixed Effect Model (FEM)* is a model that most right for used in this analysis.

Test Assumption Classic

Test Multicollinearity

Table 5. Test Results Multicollinearity

	X1	X2	X3
X1	1,000000	0.757156	0.788455
X2	0.757156	1,000000	0.882817
X3	0.788455	0.882817	1,000000

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

Results test multicollinearity show that mark correlation between variable- the independent variables are all below 0.90. This shows that there is no problem multicollinearity Which significant between independent variables in study This.

Test Heteroscedasticity

Table 6. Test Results Heteroscedasticity

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	888.2034	121.1373	7.332204	0.0000

X1	0.001745	0.002039	0.855990	0.3938
X2	-2.45E-05	3.51E-05	-0.697372	0.4870
X3	-5.61E-05	0.000118	-0.474419	0.6361

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

Results test heteroscedasticity show that mark probability Which obtained greater than 0.05. This shows that the regression model used in This study does not experience heteroscedasticity problems and is considered free from condition the.

Analysis Regression Data Panel

Following is analysis regression data panel Which use model best, that is *Fixed Effect Models*:

Table 7. Results Regression Analysis Data Fixed Panels Effect Model

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	93.47706	1.591938	58.71902	0.0000
X1	-8.98E-06	2.39E-05	-0.374974	0.7084
X2	-7.82E-07	4.65E-07	-1.682860	0.0953
X3	3.00E-07	1.38E-06	0.217973	0.8279

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

Analysis Regression Moderation (*Moderated Regression Analysis – MRA*)
Moderating variables are variables that can strengthen or weaken connection between variables independent And dependent variable.

Table 8. Results Analysis Regression Moderation

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	407.5311	92.71726	4.395418	0.0000
X1	-0.001613	0.002642	-0.610792	0.5427
X2	-1.36E-05	1.08E-05	-1.254084	0.2127
X3	6.37E-05	6.53E-05	0.975510	0.3316
Z	-19.21852	5.613705	-3.423499	0.0009
X1Z	8.36E-05	0.000137	0.611709	0.5421
X2Z	7.54E-07	5.75E-07	1.311787	0.1925
X3Z	-3.29E-06	3.38E-06	-0.972937	0.3329

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

Test Statistics

Test Q

The t test is used to determine whether each independent variable has influence significant to variable dependent on level significance 0.05. A t test probability of less than 0.05 indicates that the variable has influence significant in the regression model.

Based on the t test (partial) carried out in this research, the results are: concluded as follows:

1. Hypothesis 1 (H1): Receipt of ZISWAF Funds does not have a significant effect against BOPO. With a probability of 0.5427, which exceeds the value of 0.05. It means, reception funds ZISWAF has no effect to BOPO on company sector banking during period Year 2018.Q1–Year 2023.Q3.
2. Hypothesis 2 (H2): Wadiah current account savings have a significant influence on BOPO. With a probability of 0.2127, which exceeds the value of 0.05. It means, savings giro wadiah No influential to BOPO on company sector banking during period Year 2018.Q1–Year 2023.Q3.
3. Hypothesis 3 (H3): Murabaha income has a significant influence on BOPO. With a probability of 0.3316, which exceeds the value of 0.05. It means, Murabahah income has no effect on the company's BOPO sector banking during period Year 2018.Q1–Year 2023.Q3.
4. Hypothesis 4 (H4): Receipt of ZISWAF Funds has an influence on BOPO Which moderated by firm size. With probability as big as 0.5421, Which exceed mark 0.05. It means, firm size No own ability For moderate The influence of receiving ZISWAF funds on BOPO in sector companies banking during period Year 2018.Q1–Year 2023.Q3.
5. Hypothesis 5 (H5): Wadiah current account savings have an influence on BOPO moderated by firm size. With probability as big as 0.1925, Which exceed mark 0.05. This means that firm size does not have the ability to moderate the influence savings giro wadiah to BOPO on company sector banking during the period Year 2018.Q1–Year 2023.Q3.
6. Hypothesis 6 (H6): Murabahah income has an influence on BOPO Which moderated by firm size. With probability as big as 0.3329, Which exceed mark 0.05. It means, firm size No own ability For moderate influence income murabahah to BOPO on company sector banking during period Year 2018.Q1–Year 2023.Q3.

Test F

The F test is used to test whether the variables are independent simultaneously own influence significant to variable dependent. Following This is results from testthe F.

Table 10. Results Tes F

Prob(F-statistic)	0.000005
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Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

Results test F in study This show mark significance F as big as 0.000005, more low from 0.05. Matter This show that reception funds ZISWAF, savings wadiah demand deposits, and murabahah income simultaneously influence BOPO.

Test Coefficient Determination

Coefficient determination used For measure how much big variable independently contributed in explaining variation of variables dependent in model regression.

Table 11. Results Test Coefficient Determination

Adjusted R-squared	0.271875
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Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by writer)

Results of panel data regression analysis on BOPO as the dependent variable show that mark Adjusted R² is as big as 0.271875. Matter This indicated that around 27.1% from variable BOPO on banking can explained by variable reception funds ZISWAF, savings giro wadiah, And income murabaha.

Discussion

Influence Reception Funds ZISWAF against BOPO

Based on table 9, found mark probability reception funds ZISWAF amounted to 0.5427, which exceeds the value of 0.05. With a coefficient of -0.001613 and t- statistics -0.610792. These findings indicate that the receipt of ZISWAF funds is not influence on BOPO. This is in line with research by Iman et al. (2022) which states that zakat collection has no significant effect on BOPO in sharia banking sector companies. So hypothesis 1: receipt of funds ZISWAF No influential to BOPO accepted

Influence Savings Giro Wow against BOPO

Based on table 9, it is found that the probability value of wadiah giro savings is equal to 0.2127, which exceeds the value of 0.05. With a coefficient of -1.36E-05 and t-statistic - 1.254084. Findings This show that savings giro wadiah No own influence significant to BOPO. Matter This No in line with study by Renjani& Hendrawati (2020) Which mention that savings giro wadiah own influence positive to ROA, Which in a way No direct impact on BOPO. So hypothesis 2: Savings giro wadiah influential to BOPO rejected.

Influence Income Murabaha to BOPO

Based on table 9, found mark probability income murabahah as big as 0.3316, which exceeds the value of 0.05. With a coefficient of 6.37E-05 and t-statistic 0.975510. Findings This show that income murabahah influential against BOPO. This is not in line with research by Lubis et al. (2023) who mention that BOPO has influence positive to income margins murabahah ($p < 0.05$). So hypothesis 3: Income murabahah influential to BOPO must rejected.

Influence Reception Funds ZISWAF to BOPO with Firm Size as Moderation

Based on table 9, the interaction probability value between acceptance is found ZISWAF funds with firm size is 0.5421, which is more than 0.05. With coefficient as big as 8.36E-05 And t-statistics 0.611709. Findings This show that firm size cannot

strengthen the influence of ZISWAF fund receipts on BOPO. Matter This No in line with study by Sunarsih (2023) Which mention that on banks with a large firm size, the receipt of ZISWAF funds can have an influence greater for BOPO because more funds can be used for more banking operations. So hypothesis 4: Firm size is able to moderate reception ZISWAF funds to BOPO rejected.

Influence Savings Giro to BOPO with Firm Size as Moderation

Based on table 9, the probability value of interaction between current account savings is found wadiah with firm size is 0.1925, which is more than 0.05. With coefficients of $7.54E-07$ and t-statistic 1.311787. This finding shows that firm size cannot strengthen the influence of Wadiah demand deposits on BOPO. This is not the case in line with research by Budianti (2020) which states that the influence wadiah giro deposits against sharia banking BOPO can vary depending on on the size of the company (firm size). So hypothesis 5: Firm size is able to moderate savings wadiah giro to BOPO rejected.

Influence Income Murabaha to BOPO with Firm Size as Moderation

Based on table 9, the probability value of interaction between income was found murabahah with firm size is 0.3329, which is more than 0.05. With coefficient of $-3.29E-06$ and t-statistic -0.972937 . These findings show that firm size No can strengthen influence income murabahah to BOPO. Matter This is not in line with research by Masyithah (2022) which states that income murabahah in bank with firm size Which big tend own impact positive to BOPO Because availability funds Which big. So hypothesis 6: Firm size capable moderate income murabahah to BOPO rejected.

Influence Reception Funds ZISWAF, Savings Giro Wow, And Income Murabaha Simultaneously against BOPO

Based on data from table 10, it is concluded that the variable for receiving funds ZISWAF, savings giro wadiah, And income murabahah Own influence to BOPO, with level significance 0.000005 Which not enough from 0.05. Findings This show that reception funds ZISWAF, savings giro wadiah, And income murabahah in a way simultaneous influence BOPO. Matter This in line with study by Khatimah (2020) who states that the influence of receiving ZISWAF funds, savings giro wadiah, And income murabahah to BOPO in sector banking Sharia may vary, where funds obtained may affect operations bank And reduce cost operational in term short. So hypothesis 7: ZISWAF fund receipts, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income simultaneous affect BOPO can accepted.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on results study, found that reception funds ZISWAF, savings giro wadiah, And income murabahah No give influence significant impact on BOPO in the sharia banking sector during the 2018 period.Q1- 2023.Q3. These findings show that, despite several previous studies indicates a potential positive influence on BOPO, the results of this test did not supports this hypothesis. Besides that, firm size Also unable

moderate The relationship between these variables and BOPO is different from research previous study which shows that firm size can strengthen the influence of variable the. Although thus, in a way simultaneous reception funds ZISWAF, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income were found to have a significant effect to BOPO. Recommended for study next For consider use of additional moderating variables and involving samples from various sectors industry, so that research results can provide broader insight and representative from various economic sectors.

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